

A NEW SIMPLIFIED ASYMMETRICAL MULTILEVEL INVERTER TOPOLOGY WITH FUNDAMENTAL SWITCHING CONTROL

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Abstract— Multilevel inverters have been a widely accepted solution for high voltage and high power applications. Their performance is highly superior to that of conventional two-level inverters due to reduced harmonic distortion, lower electromagnetic interference, and higher dc link voltages. Their main disadvantage is their complexity, requiring a great number of power devices and passive components, and a rather complex control circuitry. In this paper a new inverter topology for generation of fifteen levels of output voltage with reduced number of switches is presented. This topology requires fewer components compared to existing inverters (particularly in higher levels) and requires fewer carrier signals and gate drives. The inverter is controlled by fundamental switching scheme to have a minimum power loss as compared to PWM scheme. The performance of the proposed topology is demonstrated through the simulation in MATLAB/SIMULINK platform and the results demonstrating the operation of the proposed topology as multilevel inverter is presented.

keywords— Multilevel inverter, power electronics, fundamental switching.

INTRODUCTION

Multilevel power conversion was first introduced more than two decades ago. The general concept involves utilizing a higher number of active semiconductor switches to perform the power conversion in small voltage steps. There are several advantages to this approach when compared with the conventional power conversion approach [1]. Another important feature of multilevel converters is that the semiconductors are wired in a series-type connection, which allows operation at higher voltages. However, the series connection is typically made with clamping diodes, which eliminates overvoltage concerns. Furthermore, since the switches are not truly series connected, their switching can be staggered, which reduces the switching frequency and thus the switching losses. One clear disadvantage of multilevel power conversion is the higher number of semiconductor switches required. It should be pointed out that lower voltage rated switches can be used in the multilevel converter and, therefore, the active semiconductor cost is not appreciably increased when compared with the two level cases. However, each active semiconductor added requires associated gate drive circuits and adds further complexity to the converter mechanical layout. Another disadvantage of multilevel power converters is that the small voltage steps are typically produced by isolated voltage sources or a bank of series capacitors. Isolated voltage sources may not always be readily available, and series capacitors require voltage balancing [2]. Some applications for these new converters include industrial drives, flexible ac transmission systems (FACTS), and vehicle propulsion. One area where multilevel converters are particularly suitable is that of renewable photovoltaic energy that efficiency and power quality are of great concerns for the researchers. There are several classical topologies of inverters that are reported by the researchers [3]. Multilevel inverters with reduced number of switches has also become a popular area. Inverter topologies where not all the semiconductor switches involved in output generation are also presented by the researchers [4].

This paper presents an overview of a asymmetrical fifteen level inverter topology with reduced number of switches. The dc sources are assigned with magnitude arranged in a binary fashion. The inverter is divided into two parts namely level and polarity generator whose function is to generate the necessary levels and reversing of the polarity respectively. The inverter is switched with fundamental switching strategy and the generation of control pulses is analyzed. The proposed topology is simulated using Sim power system toolbox of matlab and the results are presented.

POWER STAGE

Fig. 1 shows the power circuit of the proposed 15-level inverter topology. In conventional multilevel inverters, the power switches are operated to produce a high- frequency waveform in both positive and negative polarities. However there is no need to use all the switches for production of bipolar levels. This is the basic idea that has been put into practice by the proposed topology. The output voltage is synthesized by two stages namely level generator which is responsible for the generation of levels requires in positive polarity and secondly the polarity generator stage which is responsible for generating the polarity of the output voltage. The power semiconductor switches employed in the level generator should have high switching frequency capability for generating the required